

Big Stuff 2010

“Volunteer Training – a Success Story”

Presented by

Brian Barker

(Project Manager - Imperial War Museum Duxford)

1983 – Just Arrived at Blackpool Airport

Year 2000 – indecision !

January 2006 – Too late, only option - scrapping

A Plan is Born!

- **June 2000 The BAPC held a 'Survival Strategy Meeting' at IWM Duxford.**

(Attended by RAeS, HLF, Transport Trust, DCMS & 17 Museums)

- **2001 HLF agree to BAPC & IWM Duxford forming a joint training venture and applying for a grant.**
- **Feb 2002 BAPC Steering Group appointed to develop and manage the HLF application.**
- **September 2004 HLF Bid approved.**
- **June 2005 *National Aviation Heritage Skills Initiative* Team formed at IWM Duxford**

BRITISH AVIATION PRESERVATION COUNCIL

NATIONAL AVIATION HERITAGE SKILLS INITIATIVE

(In partnership with the Imperial War Museum Duxford)

Website Sponsor

Supported by the
Heritage Lottery Fund

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City & Guilds

Project Aims:

- **To design suitable training for volunteers in the conservation & preservation of aircraft.**
- **To gain national accreditation for the training courses.**
- **To provide that training on site at Duxford and at BAPC member organisations across the UK.**

Selection of The Training Team

1. Must be experienced instructors
2. Must be aviation engineering technicians
3. Must have credibility with the students
4. Must be seen as independent

Brian Barker – Project Manager

Joined the Royal Air Force as an apprentice 1966. Served on Vulcan BMk2 aircraft in UK and Cyprus. In 1977 become an Aircraft Servicing Chief on Victor K2 aircraft and saw service in the Falklands War. 1983 moved to the RAF Directorate of Ground Training and In 1989 moved to HQ RAF Strike Command as a training manager.

Left the RAF in 1994 moved into civilian aviation as the Operations Director of an aviation consultancy. 2001 formed his own company providing training and recruitment advice to various companies.

Keith Trigg - Instructor

Joined the Royal Air Force as an apprentice Airframe Fitter and served for 25 years. During that time he was the Supervisor and Senior Instructor at the Chinook Maintenance School. Then moved to Australia and served for 7 years as a Reservist in Royal Australian Air Force.

Immediately prior to joining the team Keith spent 10 years at Imperial War Museum Duxford, 6 years as a Conservation Officer and 4 years as the Assistant Conservation Manager.

Graham Britnell - Instructor

Joined the Royal Air Force as an Airframe Engineering Technician in 1978 and served for a total of 28 years. In that time worked on VC10s, Hunters, Buccaneers, Phantoms and Tornado aircraft spanning the environments of training, operational exercises and worldwide detachments which have included areas of conflict.

1992 – 2002 employed at RAF Cosford as the senior instructor/course design specialist. Graham is pleased to note that all the aircraft he worked on can now be found in collections and museums around the world.

Diane Barwick – Administrator 2005-2008

Prior to joining the Imperial War Museum she was a manager with a major retail company. Before joining the Team Di had spent the previous 4 years at the Museum working in a variety of administrative posts. In addition to being the initial contact for advice and information regarding the

Project Di is responsible for day to day financial control, purchasing and procurement.

Scott Downes – Administrator 2008 -2010

Prior to joining the Imperial War Museum He was a manager with Lloyds TSB working in London. He is currently attending the Open Arts College with the aim of establishing his own photographic business. He is the contact for advice and information and provides day to day financial control.

Scott has taken a leading role in co-ordinating the external validation of the project and produced the Team entry for the National Training Awards.

Development of Training Strategy

(Constraints identified from the Training Needs Analysis)

1. **Training Courses could not be longer than 1 day**
2. **Sessions must be available on any day of the week including Saturdays and Sundays**
3. **Where possible training would be delivered on site at the members location**
4. **Volunteers must have the choice as to whether or not they wished to be assessed**

NAHSI - Draft Training Strategy – June 2005

June 2005 IWM Duxford
The Transport Trust hands a sponsorship cheque
For £1000 to Barry James of the BAPC

February 2006 – The Team take delivery of their vehicle.

March 2006

Accredited by
City &

Guilds

**'I CAN
MATCH MY
PASSION
WITH MY
SKILLS'**

Skills for a brighter future

Assessment training for National Aviation Heritage Skills Initiative staff

June 20th 2006

Following a recommendation by the City & Guilds Accreditation Panel the Project Team made contact with 'Cambridge Assessment'.

1st March 2006 – Brooklands Aviation Museum.
The very first NAHSI Training course

11th April 2006 – first training session in the NAHSI classroom at IWM Duxford

29th April 2006 – Introduction to Aviation Heritage Aeroventure, Doncaster

28th June 2007 – ‘Skin Repairs 1’ at IWM Duxford for Aeroventure, Doncaster

Aircraft tools purchased for practical training sessions

August 2007 – in response to requests from the Volunteer workforce the Team became an Accredited provider of Customer Service training

18th October 2007 Mr Tony Evans of The Midland Air Museum becomes the 1000th attendee of NAHSI training.

27th October 2007 – the Project Manager presents the first BAPC Level 2 Certificates at the BAPC 40th Anniversary meeting , Rolls Royce Heritage, Derby

DAVIDSTOW AIRFIELD & CORNWALL AT WAR
MUSEUM - BAPC TRAINING 11/12 APRIL 2009

4th June 2009 – ‘Introduction to Aviation Heritage for Brooklands Aviation Museum

17th November 2009 – ‘Dismantling & Assembly’ at IWM Duxford for Duxford Aviation Society

The 'Team' – September 2010

NAHSI - Draft Training Strategy – June 2005

NAHSI Training Strategy – March 2010

City & Guilds accredited

Only presented at IWM Duxford

English Regional Tourist Boards accredited – ‘Welcome Host’

Presentations (2-3 hours) for Management & Supervisory staff

Location of BAPC Member Organisations

IWM Duxford

Statistics: 1st March 2006 – 31st Aug 2010

- **Over 700 Volunteers enrolled.**
- **29 BAPC Member Organisations involved.**
- **655 Training sessions delivered.**
- **3848 Training places filled.**
- **Over 60% of volunteers opting for City assessment.**

Volunteers Comments

- "First class - thank you very much. Most useful and informative. Look forward to the next!"
- "Excellent course content - well presented and extremely useful in the work that we do."
- "Really enjoyed the day and am very pleased that I attended. Many questions were answered that I had not even thought about asking."
- "My only regret is that I didn't take this course years ago. I now know that I have been doing much wrongly"

**EVALUATION OF THE NATIONAL AVIATION
HERITAGE SKILLS INITIATIVE
(NAHSI)**

November 2009

**Published for and on behalf of
National Aviation Heritage Skills Initiative**

**Dr A R Bennett
For the Faculty of Education
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Essex CM1 1SQ**

Extract from the Main Findings

- The NAHSI training programme has a significant and demonstrably beneficial impact on museums' exhibition work and on the volunteer workforce who are actively engaged in heritage conservation and restoration of aircraft and aircraft components.
- Evidence from representative samples in the research found training to be of real personal value for volunteers. Training is technically focused around participant competences and skill levels, and the course curricula embrace the range of skills, prior qualifications and experiences of the volunteers.

AVIATION HERITAGE SKILLS

What happens next?

Any Questions?